
SOCIO-POLITICAL SITUATION DURING THE ORGANIZATION PROCESS OF THE "BUKHARA HOUSE OF EDUCATION" IN MOSCOW

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Abstract.

In this article, an attempt was made to clarify the educational system of cultural life in Uzbekistan in the 20s and 30s of the 20th century, reforms in this area, their results, problems in the traditional education system in the Soviet era, their causes and consequences. The scope of historical research on the issues of culture and education of the USSR expanded, especially in the years of independence, and this problem was approached as objectively as possible. In the study, the activities of the progressives in Bukhara, the Jadidist movement, the overthrow of the emirate system, the establishment of the Bukhara Education House, and the processes of educational and cultural changes of the new government are highlighted.

Key words.

Pedagogical environment "Educational House of Bukhara", development, spirituality, culture, Bukhara People's Soviet Republic, Bukhara students, training of personnel, methodology.

Introduction

In the current era, the state's care for the development of education and science is very important. It is this that allows and forces us to repeatedly look at our past, study the pages of our history, study objectively and fight for the truth based on historical truth.

How was the "Bukhara House of Education" in Moscow created, how did it work, what was its work methodology, what was its role in the further development of the educational system of Uzbekistan? To open this topic, we used the works of our scientists who wrote about the education of the USSR, new materials, including archival sources, mass media, and on this basis we tried to recreate this page of our history.

After the overthrow of the emirate regime in Bukhara in September 1920, the new government headed by F. Khojayev took measures to create a modern education system. no revolution lives without education, you need a school to study, you need education, you need books - these are the truths. The structure of the government of the USSR consisted of modernists, who understood that it is possible to get rid of the mire of ignorance and backwardness by making the people literate. In this direction, in the "general rules about schools" developed in the first year of the government of the USSR, the issue of radical reform of the old education system that existed in the time of the Emirate, and making the population literate as a whole was put on the agenda [1,126].

Training of personnel for the national economy was of great importance in the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic. The young republic, despite the enormous difficulties and economic devastation during the war, effectively cooperated in the field of education with the Soviet republics: RSFSR, Turkestan ASSR and Azerbaijan. Also, the government of the USSR launched the slogans "every effort is for knowledge" and "everything is for knowledge" to develop the field of education. During its four-year history, the government of the Republic of Bukhara, consisting of Jadids, took all measures to raise our nation to the level of modern development. He considered the development of education and science as the principle of taking our rightful place in the world. He sent many talented young people to foreign countries for education.

The list of the first batch of Bukhara students sent to Moscow was compiled on August 20, 1922. There were 25 of them in total, 20 of them Uzbeks, 3 Tatars, and 2 Tajiks; the youngest was 16 years old, the oldest was 22 years old.

On September 12, 1922, students from Bukhara, led by the representative of the USSR in the RSFSR, Mukamilov, were sent to Moscow and Petrograd. The government of Bukhara did everything in its power to expand cooperation with the RSFSR in the field of personnel training. In his letter to the Deputy Commissar of Foreign Affairs L. Karakhan, the authorized representative of the USSR, Mukamilov, described in detail the issues in the field of education in the USSR and asked the Commissariat of Education of the RSFSR to establish a school in Moscow for students from Bukhara in the amount of 100 boys and 25 girls. At that time, Bukhara sent its children to study in the Caucasus and Germany. For example, in 1921, 30 students were sent to these states, and in 1922, about 50 students were sent to Germany. The representative office of the USSR in Moscow asked the People's Commissariat of Foreign Affairs of the RSFSR to help in the training of personnel

for the national economy of Bukhara in Moscow educational institutions. offered to open a small school for children from Bukhara. In turn, People's Commissar of Nations I. Stalin suggested to open a school for Bukhara children at the expense of the USSR, to organize a group of 30-35 people at the communist university in Moscow [3,469].

In April 1923, by order of the Council of People's Commissars of the USSR, the decision to establish the Bukhara "House of Education" in Moscow was entrusted to the commissariats for nationalities and education. By the decision of the RKP(b), the "Sakharo-Trust" building No. 9 near the Kremlin became the first school for students of the USSR in Moscow.

Initially, the school was designed for 75 people. With the increase in the number of students from Bukhara, there was a shortage of places in the building. Representatives of the USSR in Moscow asked the commission under the government of the RSFSR to help in determining a new place for the "Educational House" of the USSR for 200 students. By the decision of the commission on July 9, 1923, house 17 on Spiridonovka Street became the new location for the Bukhara "House of Education".

The government of the USSR under the leadership of F. Khodzhayev paid great attention to all areas of the school. On March 8, 1923, at a meeting dedicated to this issue, F. Khojajev, representative of Bukhara in the RSFSR M. Burkhanov, chairman of the Supreme Council of Economy M. Mukhitdinov, head of the organizational department in Moscow G. Khojajev, cotton Belyakov, the director of the trust, Fayzi, the head of the House of Education, took part. Based on Fayzi's report, decisions were made about the school budget, the composition of the commission to control the spending of funds, strengthening control over budget execution, attracting students from the youth of Bukhara. measures were determined (it was determined that 25 of 100 students should be girls), short-term courses were organized at the "House of Education".

In September 1923, Campenus developed a project for the expenses of the House of Education in Bukhara. It was planned to allocate 10,000 gold rubles for the repair of the building. The operation of allocating funds for the provision of the Bukhara school was carried out through intermediaries such as the Krasny Vostok plant. The lack of control over the actions of the plant managers led to the fact that the funds allocated for the repair of the school were used by the plant for other purposes. "House of Education" lacked teachers and support staff to implement a full-fledged educational process. In order to overcome the difficult situation, the

school administration developed a new expenditure plan in February 1924 in the amount of 68,000 golden rubles. Based on the standards of Moscow schools, the project provided for one teacher for every 5 students. A staff of medical staff was formed to monitor the health of the students. After that, there were changes in the project. The school expenses for 9 months were set at 65,000 gold rubles. according to all expenses for 9 months should be 195 963 golden rubles [4, 46-48].

To improve the financial situation of the Bukhara House of Education, a Board of Trustees was formed under the chairmanship of the Bukhara Consul in Moscow. The Board of Trustees covered the cost of providing 54 students in the amount of 500 gold rubles per month, which was 25% of the total expenses of the House of Enlightenment. Later, cash receipts decreased to 45 gold rubles.

During this period, Bukhara students studied in Germany, Turkey and Azerbaijan. In the spring of 1923, with the participation of Soviet representatives, a company to return students from abroad was started. Despite all the difficulties, Moscow was the largest center for training personnel for the national economy of the USSR. Until February 1924, only 172 Bukhara students studied in Moscow. They were distributed to the following educational institutions: - 20 students in the working faculty; - 16 students in the cultural and educational field; - 7 students in the military school; - 7 students at the Zarayskaya factory; - 5 students at primary and secondary schools; - 127 students at "House of Education". Of these, 50 students were planned to be placed in schools under the Moscow Department of Public Education.

At the beginning of 1924, not only students from Bukhara, but also 400 students from Turkestan studied in Moscow. The government of the USSR and its representatives in Moscow tried to help the House of Education with all their strength and capabilities. Despite the continued hostilities and economic devastation in the Bukhara region, the government of the Republic tried to provide the school with all the necessary things. A year after the establishment of the "House of Education" of Bukhara in Moscow, its achievements and shortcomings became clear, directions for improving the school's work were determined. The representatives of Bukhara intended to solve the current issues of the internal and external life of the school. First of all, the school should be subordinated directly to the Ministry of Education of the USSR, appoint a responsible employee to solve organizational issues, to be in constant contact with the Ministry of Public Education, and all structures of the school it was necessary to establish full control

of the authorized representative, to increase the annual budget of the school to 200 thousand gold rubles.

On May 18, 1924, the jubilee of Bukhara's "House of Education" was celebrated in Moscow. A decision was made to elect I.V. Stalin, N.K. Krupskaya, G.V. Chicherin, and F. Khodjaev as honorary heads of the school. It was the first and last holiday in the history of the House of Education of the USSR in Moscow. In the summer and autumn of 1924, the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic disappeared from the political arena with the delimitation of the national state in Central Asia.

Conclusion

Based on the above-mentioned opinions and considerations, first of all, a clearer understanding of the developed scientific and pedagogical environment of the Bukhara "House of Education" in Moscow, the Bukhara "House of Education", which played an important role for the cultural and spiritual development of the USSR in 1920-1924. The contribution of the genesis of development and reforms in the field of education to the development of spiritual life and pedagogical ideas of that time is of considerable importance. This means that it is important to study the center of enlightenment, which has left an indelible mark on the pages of our history, such as the Bukhara "House of Education" in a separate research style.

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